

STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP PRACTICE AND RELATIONSHIP WITH SCHOOL REPUTATION: A MODEL VALIDATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the impact of the strategic leadership practices of educational school leaders attached to secondary schools on the school reputation in Malaysia. It is to validate the proposed model of Strategic Leadership Practices which consist of the subdimensions of Organizational Activities and Individual Abilities. The model of School Reputation is also to be validated. The study is also to investigate whether there is a correlation between the Strategic leadership Practices of the school leaders of secondary schools with the school reputation. The population of the study is the educational school leaders of secondary schools in Malaysia. It is approximately more than 19,000 secondary schools in Malaysia that each leads at least by 8 top - to - bottom level of educational leaders. The population is massive and the sample size of 379 is involved in the study. The stratified random sampling technique is applied and 6 – point Likert scale questionnaire is used as the instrument in data collection process. It is the finding that, the model of Strategic Leadership Practices is valid and reliable to be implemented. Besides, there is a positive relationship between the Strategic Leadership Practices of school

leaders with school reputation. It is to propose the implementation of the strategic leadership practices by the school leaders as it imposes positive implications on the school reputation.

Keywords: Educational School Leaders; Strategic Leadership; Organizational Activities; Individual Abilities; Secondary School Reputation

INTRODUCTION

Leadership skills when practiced strategically by the school educational school leaders contribute to great positive impacts on any organization and educational leaders have great influence on learning institution's achievement and performance. There are literatures highlight the positive impacts of strategic leadership practices practiced by school leaders on schools (Davies, 2004;2006 Davies and Davies 2010; Eacott,2011; Eacott, 2010a). The literatures focus on the strategic leadership skills which determine the student and school performance. In the aspect of education development, educational school leaders have important roles that contribute to overall reputation of the school. It is the focus that the educational leaders to be well trained and armed with essential leadership skills for enable the school leaders to lead the schools and to achieve the education aspirations strategically. Schools need to be led and managed strategically in the aim to fulfil the agenda to improve performance and to achieve reputation desired.

In the purpose to achieve desirable level of reputation, the roles of the educational leaders are vital and necessary. The strategic educational leaders facilitate in goal attainment and sustain organizational improvement (Davies & Davies, 2010; Davies, 2006). The school leaders have major responsibilities to define their current reputation, strategize, and execute necessary measures and processes for better improvement of the current reputation. Strategic educational leaders lead the schools to compete and survive to achieve desirable performance as to ensure the schools to be famed and renowned. Apart from that, school leaders lead and motivate not only the students but also the teaching team to work together and achieve excellence and accomplish the goal of reputation. Based on the previous literatures, strategic leadership practices impose positive impacts on educational (Davies, 2006; Davies and Davies, 2010). It

is suggested that the practice of strategic leadership contribute to performance that owns the capability to enhance school reputation.

The major aim of this research is to examine the relationship between the strategic leadership practices practiced by school educational leaders on secondary school reputation. The research is intentionally to ascertain the following objectives:

1. To validate the proposed model of the of secondary school educational leader strategic leadership practice.
2. To validate the proposed model of secondary school reputation.
3. To measure the relationship between the strategic leadership practices of secondary school educational leaders and the reputation of secondary schools.

The hypotheses of the study are as follows;

H1: The secondary school educational leader strategic leadership practice model is valid and reliable.

H2: The secondary school reputation model is valid and reliable.

H3: There is a relationship between the secondary school educational leader strategic leadership practice and secondary school reputation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of School Strategic Leadership

School strategic leadership is a crucial element in developing schools effectively. Strategic leadership has connection with strategic functions and leadership functions. It is also the means which link between strategic processes or activities to operational planning. It is defined as the ability to define vision and moral purpose, and translate them into action. Strategic leaders build and set up the direction and manage the capacity of resources as to achieve positive change (Davies and Davies, 2010; Davies, 2006). This needs the school leaders to practice transformational change for the sake of betterment. Davies and Davies (2010) and Davies (2006) proposed the framework and the dimension of effective educational strategic leaders which will be manipulated as the constructs of the study.

Activities of Strategic School Leaders

The school leaders are obligated to carry out some organizational activities for the school to perform better and achieve the reputation as aspired. There are activities which are theoretically categorized as Organizational Activities (OA). The activities are as the following;

1. Strategic leaders create vision and future school direction (SLSSD)

School leaders have the obligation of performing the activity which relates to a strategic process of definition of strategy in which the leaders set the direction of the school. It is proposed that the direction is set to accomplish the short-term strategic view of three to five years into future. Vision created must be able to attract commitment, instill the sense of meaning or purpose and establish the standard of excellent (Davies and Davies, 2010). Leaders are to move away from current perspective and think about to develop a medium-term perspective (Davies, 2006). This involves some planning approaches to build capacity for better understanding the accomplishment and feasibility of future possibilities. School leaders are not only looking forwards from the present but also setting up a strategic mental picture and envision of what the school to look like in the future (Davies and Davies, 2010). For the implementation of these efforts and processes, it is a priority that the leaders must set some guidelines and frameworks of ways of moving forwards to achieve the future direction and to accomplish the vision. School leaders at this point are to rethink the present and future school operation, decide how to advance from present to desired future and to involve in conceptualization processes (Davies and Davies, 2006).

2. Strategic leaders exert strategic influence (SLESI)

It is crucial to build and develop the capacity to deliver the strategy. Powerful understanding should be built within the staff to enable them to participate in strategic implementation. Educational leaders ought to be passionate for education and exhibit it for others to have moral purpose as for them to get involved and then establish understanding. Hence, trust, beliefs, and integrity can be established (Davies and Davies, 2010). School leaders must possess the ability to influence and persuade others to commit their effort towards embracing changes. This needs the mutual commitment as the whole staff will be doing and performing tasks together in achieving the school's desired goals. Leaders should be able to create a culture which everyone shares

responsibility for building the future. Besides, leaders empower the people and align the people and the organization strategically together. Davies and Davies (2010) and Davies (2006) proposed ABCD Approach that may build understanding within the staff to contribute and commit. The approach suggests the strategies of articulating the goals and vision, building common understanding, creating mental map of future, and defining the desired outcomes.

4. Strategic leaders are strategic talent developer (SLTD)

In developing strategic capabilities, educational leaders should adapt the ideas of core competencies and strategic capabilities. In the aim of achieving the core competencies, leaders are to develop longer term abilities and develop the existing skills of the people in schools. High performance learning environment must be provided to add the value to learning processes. Leaders are encouraged to produce other leaders by providing leadership opportunities and provide in – house development programs (Davies and Davies, 2010). It is to recommend that leaders to develop the learning culture in staff, problem solving teamwork approach, and challenge the status quo to create different roles among the educators. When facing with new challenges, leaders can manipulate and implement the capabilities and not just to rely on the current skills of the members of the unit. Sustaining and developing staff is vital in longer term (Davies and Davies, 2010).

5. Strategic leaders balance the strategic and the operation (SLBSO)

Effective educational strategic leaders must be able to balance long term strategy with the short-term operation. Leaders are required to practice regular review of the benchmarks that are set yet to avoid seeing short term benchmarks as the outcomes. It is compulsory to be done is that short term benchmarks should not be seen as separate from the long-term benchmarks. Short term operations are seen as the guideline for the long-term strategy as short-term benchmarks should be integrated to long term objectives and outcomes (Davies and Davies, 2010). It is vital to balance short term and long-term benchmarks as this gives some benefits for the schools to achieve successful and sustainable operation and performance. It is quite a challenge for educational leaders to implement this activity as managing the present enables them building capacity for the future.

6. Strategic leaders deliver strategic action (SLDSA)

Most strategic leaders are capable to develop set of plans yet not many are able to translate the plans into actions. The leaders should be able to see ahead and to see through (Davies, 2006: 2003). That means that leaders can focus on limited number of key issues and work to resolve such issues. Strategic leaders are not only able to build sense of purpose and direction but also to turn the plan into action reality. It is their obligation to establish credibility for embracing change. It is to propose that effective school educational leaders to set clear objectives, align the people to implement the strategy, make reflection and feedback, and deliver the strategic change that might occur (Davies and Davies, 2010). There is a need to continue implementing strategic vision and strategic ability in the preparation to translate the strategy into action and reality. School strategic leaders should determine the change needed to be articulated, plan the implementation, and establish the outcomes.

6. Strategic leaders define strategic measures of success (SLDMS)

It is crucial for educational strategic leaders define the measure of success. Leaders need to establish the criteria and find measures to evaluate the established criteria. The data should be available for the educational leaders to refer to such as the test and examination results. As to achieve the measure of success, active involvement of students in learning must be created. Not only that, teachers and staff should be ensured to have positive and active involvement in reflection and dialogues for them to discuss ideas and build professional learning community. Educational leaders must ensure that the staff and teachers learn from each other to reflect on success and failure. Teachers are given the responsibilities and must be able to make own decision. Strategic leaders at school should envisage and articulate what success would be or look like in five years for instance (Davies and Davies, 2010).

All these activities proposed are relevant to the factors and the dimensions which concern on the implementation of strategic leadership and the educational leaders' responsibilities to lead strategically focused schools. The activities of strategic leaders are also referred to organizational activities (OA).

Personal Characteristics of Strategic School Leaders

Apart from the organizational activities, school strategic leaders must possess and portray some outstanding personal characteristics as the strategic leaders. Davies and Davies (2010) and

Davies (2006) proposed few major personal attributes which referred as Individual Abilities (IA):

1. Strategic leaders are strategic thinkers (SLST)

Leaders are always able to see that the organization can be able to perform better in different ways in the future. They are to see the school operation in the broader concept in present and the future (Davies and Davies, 2010). The current situation is always challenged and there is the need to improve the mission and performance for better future by scanning the current environment, envisioning the future, setting the future, and engaging in strategic thinking to innovatively implement strategies. They must always think beyond current views and perspective as they build mental models to frame their own and others' understanding for current and the future direction (Davies, 2006). They maximize the opportunities, relate the knowledge for change, and have good ideas for outstanding performance of schools. These are done as to meet up and embrace new challenge, new skills, and new strategies for embracing change.

2. Strategic leaders are strategic learners (SLSL)

It is essential for every strategic leader of a school to be the learners who always seek for knowledge and insight. They set up the school framework of strategies, consider the culture, structure, and system to support learning. Learning must be set to be aligned with leadership roles as to improve and develop. Knowledge transfer should be promoted and deep learning should be taken place for wisdom and understanding. Strategic conversation is encouraged to be practiced as it is the leaders' task that all staff and teachers engage in discussion for them to enhance skills and knowledge in unity and learning needs must be articulated as well (Davies and Davies, 2010).

3. Strategic leaders are values driven (SLVD)

Strategic leaders of schools should always involve strategy processes that are based on the values and beliefs to enhance the learning processes of students. The vision articulated must be based on core values and beliefs that makes the staff and teachers to feel energized to share responsibilities and accountabilities. Educational leaders are to establish moral culture, values, and the moral characteristics among the staff in the schools. The clarity of the individual's values does contribute to the different level of commitment towards the students and the school. Davies and Davies (2010) proposed

some moral culture to be practiced such as honesty, integrity, promise keeping, loyalty, fairness, concern, respect, law abiding, pursuit of excellence, and personal accountability. School leaders are to act within the moral framework in formulating strategy and executing strategic leadership. The moral and values is the factor to define effective strategic leadership practices at schools. This contributes to positive commitment of the staff and teachers that enables to bring some positive changes.

The proposed model of strategic leadership has some contributions and implications on the effectiveness of the school. If the school leaders focus on the sustainability and school reputation, it is paramount that the strategic dimensions of the leadership capability to be developed and implemented.

The Concept of School Reputation

School reputation does exist that should be managed and measured homogeneously (Sager et al., 2014) as it can be a part of the school dynamics for the schools also have to display corporate image and reputation. It is also concluded that school reputation is the mixture of stakeholders' opinions and attitudes towards the schools. In the aspiration to reach the goals, schools are to practice some types of social value. Reputation is understood as the combination features and characteristics which are connected to perception and image and is the combination of the culture and the climate impacts on schools' image internally and externally. Every school wants to be recognized and well reputed of their distinctive features that make the school outstanding. Hence, school reputation is crucial even well regarded than its' real quality, which is in turn influences future students of the school.

Dimensions of School Reputation

Initially, the study on reputation was mostly done on corporate reputation. It is developed ever since with more scholars have interest to conduct the study on academic and school reputation. Walsh and Beatty (2007) suggested that reputation is all about overall evaluation of organization based on customers' reaction to goods, services, communication activities and the interaction among the people in an organization. They further developed the dimensions as the measurement for reputation. There are five dimensions proposed by Walsh and Beatty (2007):

1. Customer orientation – the perception the customers have on the willingness to satisfy their needs.
2. Good employer – the perception on how the employers treat the employees and focus on their interest.
3. Reliable and financially strong – the perception on competence, solidity, and profitability.
4. Product and service quality – the perception on quality, innovation, value, and reliability.
5. Social and environmental responsibility – concern on positive roles played in society.

Skallerud (2011) had revised the proposed dimensions and manipulated the dimensions in the study to measure parent – based school reputation. Out of five dimensions four dimension were chosen and adapted based on the school and academic context. For the study, the four emergent dimensions developed by Skallerud (2011) will be manipulated to measure the school reputation. The four emergent dimensions proposed are:

Skallerud (2011) had proposed dimensions to measure parent – based school reputation. For the study, the four emergent dimensions developed by Skallerud (2011) will be manipulated to measure the school reputation. The four emergent dimensions proposed in secondary school reputation (SSR) are:

1. Parents orientation (SRPO)

It is referred to parents' perception on the school's willingness to satisfy their need in the aspects of children and learning process. The more satisfied the parents are, the better they perceive school reputation. Parents are satisfied when they are happy with the academic achievement of their children and the overall school performance.

2. Learning quality (SRLQ)

This dimension refers to parents' perception of the quality of teaching activities. Learning quality is the strongest dimension perceived by parents (Skallerud, 2011). Parents anticipate their children to involve in excellent teaching delivered by effective teachers.

3. Good teachers (SRGT)

The dimension of good teachers is about how the school management treat the teachers and the perception on teachers' competences. Teachers are perceived as having instructional competences, wisdom, desire, and commitment and have emotional appeal who are caring and warmth and have good behaviour and inspire the students.

4. School environment (SRSE)

This dimension is about parents' concern on the aspects of safety and the climate at the school. Parents anticipate the school is a conducive and a safe place for their children to learn. The sense of the security is prioritized as strong discipline and low level of violence in a school ensures the safety for the students to involve in classroom activities.

Reputation is seen as an uncontrollable element; it must be well managed yet the level of competitiveness increases as to sustain success and accomplishment.

METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

As for the research, the population involved are the school leaders / administrators or the leadership teams in Malaysian secondary schools. The educational school leaders who are also teachers are positioned to several posts to lead and manage the schools. They are positioned and promoted as:

1. The Principal
2. The Senior Assistant of Administration/ Curriculum
3. The Senior Assistant of Co – Curriculum
4. The Senior Assistant of Student Affair
5. The Head Departments of Language, Humanity, Vocational, and Mathematics and Science.

There are 8 top - to - bottom level of educational school leaders in each secondary school in Malaysia. There are more than 2458 secondary schools located throughout Malaysia that involved massive number of populations. The number of samples involved in the study is 379 and the stratified random sampling technique is applied as the population is divided into discrete and distinctive sub population.

Research Instrument

The study uses questionnaire as for the research instrument which is adopted and adapted based on the existing literature on the chosen strategic leadership theory and the school reputation theory. The adapted 6-point Likert scale is applied that allows respondents to consider the items very carefully and could decide on their preference either leans negatively or positively. The validation of questionnaire including item adaptation and modification, content validation, and item refinement are carried out. The questionnaires were distributed to the selected schools face to face and via express mails to the selected schools in Malaysia. There are valid and normal 379 samples measured and analysed for the study.

RESULTS

Measurement Model and Structural Model Analyses of SLP and SSR

The Strategic Leadership Practice (SLP) model of the study is discussed in the aspects of measurement model which involved the data presentation on the indicator validity, internal consistency, and construct validity. Other than that, there are also the results presentation on the evaluation of structural model that involved collinearity of assessment, path coefficients, total effects, and coefficient determination (R Square).

Indicator Reliability

Indicator reliability of the constructs is derived from the test results of outer loading generated by the PLS SEM software that indicates the values of the analysis to be within the threshold that not less 0.708 (Hair et al.,2022).

Based on the Figure 1, for the construct of Organizational Activities (OA) subdimension of SLP, all the items in SLSSD are calculated for the loadings more than the threshold that are ranging from 0.726 to 0.805, the loadings of 0.716 to 0.810 for SLESI, the values of 0.794 to 0.843 for SLBSO, and for SLTD it is ranging from 0.743 to 0.823. As for the SLDSA, the outer loadings are calculated for 0.722 to 0.811, SLDMS for 0.728 to 0.824 and SLDSA for 0.722 to 0.811.

Figure 1: Factor loadings in OA Subdimension of SLP

Based on the outer loading analysis, all the items in OA model are calculated as reliable for the values of the factor loadings are in accordance to the threshold of greater than 0.708 (≥ 0.708). The highest value of factor loading is for the item of with the loading of 0.843 (BSO4) and the lowest loading value is 0.716 for ESI8.

For the subdimension of IA which is SLST, the values of factor loading are from 0.768 to 0.832, items in SLSL are valued from 0.713 to 0.833 and the values of 0.768 to 0.867 are for SLVD. The highest factor loading is in VD3 in SLVD and the lowest is the item SL8 in SLSL (0.713).

Figure 2: Factor loadings in IA Subdimension of SLP

The values for the loadings of items in SRPO in SSR are ranged from 0.736 to 0.848, SRLQ items are ranged from 0.723 to 0.870, the values of 0.805 to 0.865 are for the items of SRGT, and for items of SRSE, the values are from 0.751 to 0.860.

Figure 3: Factor loadings of SSR constructs

The Convergent Validity and Internal Consistency Reliability of SLP and SSR Models

The convergent validity of constructs is measured based on the composite reliability (CR) of Rho_ A and Rho_ C including the AVE. In addition, the internal consistency reliability of the constructs is measured based on the analyses of the test results on Cronbach’s Alpha. The threshold for both composite reliabilities and the internal consistency reliability must be greater than 0.7 (≥ 0.7) (Ringle et al., 2023; Hair et al., 2022).

Based on the analyses, the values of the composite reliability of the constructs are within the range of threshold of 0.7. Table 1 presents the values of the analyses of the convergent validity and internal consistency reliability of the constructs. The values of CR (Rho_ A) of Organizational Ability constructs indicate the values higher than suggested threshold which is 0.871. The construct of SLBSO obtains the highest value of 0.887 and the construct of SLTD records the least value of 0.803. The subdimension of Individual Abilities (IA) of SLP indicates that SLSL gains the highest value of 0.919 and the lowest Rho_ A of the subdimension is 0.886 for SLVD. For the Secondary School Reputation, the SRGT is valued at 0.896 as the highest in the construct and SRPO obtains the lowest value of Rho_ A (0.870).

As for the composite reliability of Rho_ C, all values computed for all the constructs are within the range and even higher than the threshold for reliability. The highest rho_ C value for subdimension of OA is for construct SLBSO with the value of 0.912 and the lowest value is 0.867 for construct SLSSD. The highest value of Rho_ C for subdimension of IA is 0.932 for

the construct of SLSL and the lowest reliability value of this subdimension is for construct SLVD with the value of 0.911. For the Secondary School Reputation, the SRGT is valued at 0.922 as the highest in the construct and SRPO obtains the lowest value of Rho_C (0.884).

All constructs in subdimension OA have obtained the value of AVE more than 0.5. The construct of SLBSO has the highest AVE which is 0.676 and SLSSD is the lowest AVE in subdimension of OA (0.566). The subdimension of IA consists of the constructs with the values of the threshold which are 0.672, 0.649, and 0.603 for SLVD, SLST, and SLSL respectively. The dimension of Secondary School Reputation has the constructs with desirable values of AVE. The highest construct value of AVE in this dimension is SRGT which is 0.704 and the lowest AVE is 0.654 for the construct of SRLQ.

The internal consistency reliability of the constructs of the respecified model is measured based on the analyses of the test results on Cronbach's Alpha. All the measured values of the consistency reliability of Cronbach's Alpha are within the threshold of the reliability. For the SLP subdimension of OA, the highest reliability value is the construct of SLBSO with the reliability value of 0.881 and the lowest value is 0.800 for the dimension of SLTD. Whereas, the construct of SLSL has the highest value of 0.917 and 0.878 is the lowest value of SLVD in subdimension of IA. As for the dimensions in Secondary School Reputation, SRGT obtains 0.895 as the highest reliability value of alpha and SRPO has the lowest value of 0.831.

Table 1: Convergent Validity and Consistency Reliability of Constructs

Latent Variable	Cronbach's alpha	CR (Rho_A)	CR (Rho_C)	AVE
SLP				
OA	0.870	0.871	0.900	0.562
SLSSD	0.808	0.809	0.867	0.566
SLESI	0.856	0.857	0.893	0.582
SLTD	0.800	0.803	0.869	0.625
SLBSO	0.881	0.887	0.912	0.676
SLDSA	0.856	0.857	0.893	0.582
SLDMS	0.850	0.850	0.893	0.625
IA	0.951	0.951	0.956	0.560

SLST	0.892	0.893	0.917	0.649
SLSL	0.917	0.919	0.932	0.603
SLVD	0.878	0.886	0.911	0.672
SSR	0.928	0.928	0.938	0.559
SRPO	0.831	0.870	0.884	0.657
SRLQ	0.867	0.871	0.904	0.654
SRGT	0.895	0.896	0.922	0.704
SRSE	0.875	0.876	0.909	0.668

The Relationship of the Latent Variables

For the structural model analyses, the results of the Path Coefficient and Coefficient Determination are presented and discussed. The structural analyses of coefficients are carried out to determine the relationship among the constructs as to support the hypotheses. In addition to that, the variance inflation factor (VIF) values are presented to indicate if there is any issue among the predictor constructs. The VIF value close to 3 or lower (≤ 3) shows that the constructs are in the state of ideal (Hair et al.,2022;2019)

For the path coefficient values of the data, all the results of the analysis point out that the variable have the value of within the range of -1 - +1 and are positively correlated. Based on Table 2, for the subdimension of OA in the dimension of SLP, the highest value of its path coefficient is with the SLDSA (0.988), followed by SLBSO (0.729), SLESI (0.687), SLDMS (0.666), SLTD (0.633), and the least coefficient is with SLSSD which is 0.630. For the relationship with subdimension of IA, SLSL records the highest value of 0.945, followed by SLST and SLVD with the values of 0.892 and 0.863 respectively. SLP has moderate relationship of coefficient of 0.450 with the Secondary School Reputation. The dependent variable of Secondary School Student obtains the values of coefficient of 0.913, 0.903, 0.832 and 0.451with SRGT, SRSE, SRLQ and SRPO respectively.

As for the collinearity between the constructs, the values of collinearity for the most paths are below 3. Based on Table 2, most of the paths have the values of 1.00 except for the relationship of SAP with SSR and SLP with SSR which both have the same value of 1.368. As the values

of VIF are in the range of the threshold, it is to prove that there no issue exists in the collinearity among the constructs.

Table 2: Path Coefficients and the VIF of Constructs

Constructs	Path Coefficient	VIF
SLP -> OA	0.872	1.00
SLP-> IA	0.892	1.00
OA -> SLBSO	0.729	1.00
OA -> SLDMS	0.666	1.00
OA -> SLDSA	0.988	1.00
OA -> SLESI	0.687	1.00
OA -> SLSSD	0.630	1.00
OA -> SLTD	0.633	1.00
IA -> SLSL	0.945	1.00
IA -> SLST	0.892	1.00
IA -> SLVD	0.863	1.00
SLP -> SSR	0.450	1.368
SSR -> SRPO	0.451	1.00
SSR -> SRLQ	0.832	1.00
SSR -> SRGT	0.913	1.00
SSR -> SRSE	0.903	1.00

The Total Effects of the Constructs

The results of total effects analysis are used to discuss and assess on the significance and relevance of the structural relationship and correlations among the constructs. It is also to evaluate how strong the driver constructs (SLP) influence the key target of dependent variable (SSR).

The SLP is calculated to have the total effect with SSR at 0.681 which is the moderate positive relationship. In the SLP subdimension of OA, the strongest relationship of OA is the highest

with the construct of SLDSA (0.988), followed by the SLBSO (0.729), SLESI (0.687), SLDMS (0.666), and SLTD (0.633). The least value of relationship of the subdimension is between the OA with SLSSD which is 0.630. The relationship between the OA with SSR is measured at 0.556 which is also a moderate positive relationship.

As for the subdimension of IA in SLP of independent variables, the results on the total effects on the constructs of SLSL, SLST, and SLVD show strong relationship values. They are valued at 0.945, 0.892, and 0.863 respectively. Overall, the total effect of IA with SSR is 0.623 which is a moderate correlation.

The dimension of SSR latent variables show positive effects in the relationships with the constructs. The four constructs in this dimension show satisfactory level of total effect of the relationship between the SSR with the SRPO, SRLQ, SRGT, and SRSE. The total effects of all these constructs in SSR are valued at 0.913 for the effect with SRGT as the strongest correlation, 0.903 with SRSE, 0.832 with SRLQ and the least total effect is with SRPO that measured at 0.451.

The values of the total effects recorded indicate the positive correlation between the constructs and the variables. Thus, the test results on the relationship effects of the constructs enable to respond to the hypotheses and the research questions positively.

Table 3: Total Effects of Constructs

Constructs	Total Effects
SLP -> OA	0.872
SLP -> IA	0.892
SLP -> SSR	0.681
OA -> SLDSA	0.988
OA -> SLESI	0.687
OA -> SLTD	0.633
OA -> SLDMS	0.666
OA -> SLSSD	0.630
OA -> SLBSO	0.729
OA -> SSR	0.556

IA -> SLSL	0.945
IA -> SLST	0.892
IA-> SLVD	0.863
IA->SSR	0.623
SSR -> SRGT	0.913
SSR -> SRLQ	0.832
SSR -> SRSE	0.903
SSR ->SRPO	0.451

The Significance of the Model

As the results of the bootstrapping procedure, a significant model is created based on the values of both in measurement and structural analyses. The procedure of data estimation on duplicate sample has produced more accurate and significant values of CFA. Based on the CFA values calculated via the bootstrapping procedure. In Table 4, it is to further prove that the SLP model and SSR model of the study possess the validity and reliability values which are significant.

The results of bootstrapping have shown that all the values of R Square for all SLP dimensions are positive that all the constructs have positive relationships ranging from weak coefficient to strong coefficient values. The weakest coefficient of the construct is SLSSD in subdimension of OA which is the SLSSD (0.397) yet the construct is measured as valid and reliable (AVE = 0.566, Cronbach's Alpha = 0.808, Rho_A = 0.809, Rho_C = 0.867) and highly significant at 0.000. The construct with the highest coefficient determination is 0.976 for the construct SLDSA of OA (AVE = 0.582, Cronbach's Alpha = 0.856, Rho_A = 0.857, Rho_C = 0.893). The other constructs in the SLP variables are figured at the values within the thresholds of reliability and validity with high significant values.

The dependent variable of SSR has recorded the value of 0.609 for the R Square. The strongest coefficient is seen in the construct of SRGT with the value of 0.834 (AVE = 0.704, Cronbach's Alpha = 0.895, Rho_A = 0.896, Rho_C = 0.922). The least value of the R Square is for the construct of SRPO (0.203) yet with the satisfactory values of AVE = 0.657, Cronbach's Alpha = 0.831, Rho_A = 0.870, Rho_C = 0.884.

For the R Square analysis that measures the relationship and explanatory power, the test of the bootstrapping procedure indicates the values of greater than 0. The values have proven the constructs have positive effect size of correlation and the constructs' values of the validity and reliability show that the models are valid and reliable. All the constructs of the latent variables exhibit high significant values in both validity and reliability of proposed models (p values of 0.000).

Table 4: The Significant of the CFA Measurements

Constructs	R2	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho_ A	Rho_ C	AVE	P
SLP						
OA	0.760	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.000
SLSSD	0.397	0.808	0.809	0.867	0.566	0.000
SLESI	0.472	0.856	0.857	0.893	0.582	0.000
SLTD	0.401	0.800	0.803	0.869	0.625	0.000
SLBSO	0.532	0.881	0.887	0.912	0.676	0.000
SLDSA	0.976	0.856	0.857	0.893	0.582	0.000
SLDMS	0.443	0.850	0.850	0.893	0.625	0.000
IA						
IA	0.796	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.000
SLST	0.820	0.903	0.904	0.923	0.633	0.000
SLSL	0.905	0.924	0.926	0.936	0.592	0.000
SLVD	0.745	0.878	0.886	0.911	0.672	0.000
SSR						
SSR	0.609	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.000
SRPO	0.203	0.831	0.870	0.884	0.657	0.000
SRLQ	0.649	0.867	0.871	0.909	0.715	0.000
SRGT	0.834	0.895	0.896	0.922	0.704	0.000
SRSE	0.816	0.875	0.876	0.909	0.668	0.000

DISCUSSION

This subsection discusses on the findings of the study on answering the research questions and to prove the hypotheses of the study.

Based on the factor loading analysis, it is to ascertain that items of the constructs in the latent variable are reliable. All the items in OA and IA of SLP model are calculated as reliable for the values of the factor loadings are in accordance to the threshold of greater than 0.708 (≥ 0.708). Likewise, all the items in SRR model are also calculated with the reliable values of factor loadings. In addition, according to the results of the convergent validity and internal consistency reliability of SLP and SSR model, all the values of the analyses fall within the thresholds set as to achieve validity and reliability of the proposed models of the study. Thus, at this stage, the values of these validity and reliability measurements are the evident to establish valid and reliable models of SLP and SSR. Hence, this supports the hypotheses on models' validity and reliability and answer the research questions on the similar concerns.

Furthermore, the values of the total effects recorded indicate the positive correlation between the constructs and the variables. Thus, the test results on the relationship effects of the variables enable to respond to the hypotheses and the research questions positively.

CONCLUSION

Based on the measurement and structural model analyses conducted, the test results have proven that the hypotheses (H1 and H2) of the study are supported and the values do not violet the thresholds to establish a fit model of the study. Likewise, through the results of path coefficient and total effects of the variables, the hypothesis of H3 is well supported by the results of analyses of these measurements. Thus, the results have shown that the model of Strategic Leadership Practices of school leaders and the model of the School Reputation are valid and reliable. Besides, there is positive relationship between the strategic leadership practices with school reputation.

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